
South African Parents' Perspectives on Learner Discipline

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ABSTRACT

One of the under-researched aspects of the problem of learner discipline in South African schools is that of family-related factors. This article reports on research attempting to fill this void. A semi-self-constructed questionnaire for discovering South African parents' perspectives regarding the discipline of their children, both at home and in school, was applied to a sample of parents. The questionnaire comprised the subscale 'authoritative parenting style', a section pertaining to 'the state of discipline of their children at home' and a third scale, covering the aspect 'discipline in school'. The mean score registered on the second subscale 'the state of discipline at home' was found to be high (3.67 out of a maximum of 4.00). The respondents apparently perceived the state of discipline of their children at home to be very favourable. The score on the third scale ('discipline in school') was also high, namely 3.27 out of a maximum of 4.00, indicating that the respondents were very positive about the state of learner discipline in schools. The correlation between these two scales was also found to be high: the parents who had a positive view of the state of discipline at home tended to have a concomitantly positive view of the state of discipline at school. Close examination revealed that both these subscales are aligned with an authoritative parenting style. Some recommendations flow from these findings.

Keywords: Authoritative parenting style, Discipline at home, Discipline in school, Ecological systems theory, Parental views

Introduction

Learner discipline, along with the management thereof, has been a serious problem in South African schools for some time now (Motseke, 2020). According to Padayachee and Ntombizandile (2022, p. 1), “South African schools are faced with an arguably insurmountable problem as a culture of indiscipline continually increases in schools”. To fully understand this problem and devise strategies to address it, the factors that cause or lead to the problem should be understood. Completed research on learner discipline in schools has revealed six sets of factors that cause or, at least, correlate with the current state of learner discipline in schools (Wolhuter et al., 2019): learner-related factors, teacher-related factors, school-related factors, family-related factors, society-related factors and education system-related factors. Of these, the one set of factors that have hitherto received minimal attention from the scholarly community is the one pertaining to family-related issues (see Wolhuter & Van der Walt, 2020). This article reports on research attempting to fill this lacuna.

Conceptual-theoretical framework

As far as could be established, no extensive theory about the role of parents in connection with the state of school discipline has yet been developed apart from the work reported in the Elton Report (1989) on discipline in schools in England, confirming the fact that the parental and family background should be recognised as one of the determinants of discipline in schools. This section of the article goes a step further by dealing in more detail with such parent-related factors: the example set by the parents when the children are at home; parental duties and concerns regarding the discipline and disciplining of their children at home and at school; and especially parents’ views regarding this issue.

Bronfenbrenner’s (1979) ecological systems theory was deemed to be a useful frame for approaching the issue of discipline. Bronfenbrenner distinguishes five levels or spheres of influence in a child’s development, from the closest to the most distant level (Bronfenbrenner, 1979, 1994). The microsystem, the first sphere of influence in a child’s development, consists of the family, school, immediate environment or neighbourhood and peers (Bronfenbrenner, 1979). The family, according to Bronfenbrenner, is the primary influence on a child’s development and behaviour. The parents are the most proximal to the child during his or her formative years and they, together with the school, have an impact on the child’s development. The immediate neighbourhood in which the child grows up, in conjunction with the family and school, is the context in which the child’s primary socialisation occurs. The second level distinguished by Bronfenbrenner (1994), the mesosystem, is a system of interrelationships or linkages between processes that take place between two or more settings containing the developing person. The mesosystem is a system of linkages between processes occurring, for instance, “between the family and school, the school and workplace” (Bronfenbrenner, 1994, p. 40). Therefore, what occurs in the child’s family may influence the way the child behaves in school, and vice versa. The third level, the exosystem, “comprises the linkages and processes taking place between two or more settings at least one of which does not contain the developing person” (Bronfenbrenner, 1994, p. 40), but “in which events occur that affect or are affected by what happens in that setting” (Bronfenbrenner, 1979, p. 237). In other words, processes in settings in which the child is not involved can influence the settings occupied by the child. A good example provided by Bronfenbrenner is that the relationship between the home and a parent’s workplace may affect a child indirectly through the parent’s behaviour because of his or her experience at work. The fourth level, the macrosystem, “consists of the overarching pattern of micro-, meso-, and exosystems characteristic of a given subculture with particular reference to the belief systems, bodies of knowledge, material resources, customs, lifestyles, opportunity

structures, hazards, and life course options that are embedded in each of these broader systems” (Bronfenbrenner, 1994, p. 40). The fifth level, the chronosystem, “encompasses change or consistency over time not only in the characteristics of the person but in the environment in which that person lives” (Bronfenbrenner, 1994, p. 40). For example, changes in a child’s development stages from early childhood to adolescence may bring about several behavioural changes. Similarly, changes in the parents’ socio-economic or marital status over time would have an impact on the child’s behaviour at home and at school. Bronfenbrenner’s ecological systems model has been found to be a helpful frame to position parent- and school-related factors regarding the nature and state of learner discipline. The first two levels of his model are particularly relevant to the research reported in this article.

Parents are seen as the primary educators of their children since, in most cases, children spend the first years of their lives in their parental homes and under the supervision and care of their parents or, in the absence of the natural parents, other educators, such as caretakers. Apart from the normal physical care that should be provided to young children, parents (or those in loco parentis) must lead, guide, equip, train and unfold the potential of the youngsters entrusted to them (Nussbaum, 2011). This involvement is required to assist children to become active, productive, responsible, accountable citizens and people with integrity in their current historical context. This task and duty also entail disciplining children through loving and caring guidance so that they will be prepared to willingly follow the lead of their parents when confronted with situations in which they have to make their own ethical and moral choices.

“Discipline” in the sense discussed so far is derived from the core word “disciple”, meaning “follower”. Children should be guided and equipped to become willing followers of their educators – in the first place, their parents and, in time, also their teachers who, in the school context, in many respects assume the status of in loco parentis educators. Chairilisyah (2019) stated that the cultivation of discipline “needs to start as early as possible; starting from within the family, the educational environment, and the community environment” and that the “discipline rules that are applied to children must form an agreement between home and school” (p. 1283). The disciplining of children forms part of the overall education of children (aimed at what the ancient Greeks referred to as the *paideia* ideal) (Grayling, 2002). Many parents experience a problem with the execution of this task and duty as they have not been equipped for it. The task becomes even more daunting if one considers that primary educators should also caringly and lovingly attend to the development and unfolding of the capabilities (potential) of the youngsters (Nussbaum, 2011; Sen, 2010) and guide them to achieve personal integrity as adults later in life (Noshulwana, 2011). The disciplining of children also entails instilling in them a sense of morality. Many parents seem to guide their children intuitively to act correctly and appropriately in particular circumstances. Of even greater concern is the question of whether parents and other primary educators know and understand the various approaches to morality and whether they can guide their children to not only understand these approaches but also apply them in their future lives. The question is whether they know and understand the implications of approaches to (proper) behaviour and, hence, good discipline. Parents should expose self-awareness and enable dialogical communication to transmit exemplary moral behaviour to their children (Chairilisyah, 2019).

The teaching of social skills also has a role in the creation of a disciplined school environment. Some parents are sensitive to the teaching of social skills in schools. A study conducted by Sibanda (2018) showed that some parents did not appreciate the value of social skills because of their bias towards academic subjects and, as a result, they discouraged their children from participating in club activities. The role of parents in encouraging their children to attend to the development of social skills can improve attendance at these types of

programmes, which also teach learners about discipline. Other research projects have also indicated that some causes of disruptive behaviour are the result of poor parenting. A study by Ghazi et al. (2013), for instance, revealed that disruptive behaviour in schools could be caused by inconsistent parenting and uncaring or over-protective parents.

Parents' concerns about their children and their discipline (or indiscipline) do not end when the children start attending school. The children are confronted with a variety of new influences at school, and they need parental guidance in navigating their way through this new maze. Research is required to determine and understand all the new influences and conditions that children must cope with once they begin attending school. More to the point, this research should establish whether parents know and understand (their perceptions of) such new developments. The fact that the children now become students or learners implies that parents should also attend to the inter-institutional relationship between the parental home and the school. Furthermore, parents belonging to mainstream religions should attend to inter-institutional relationships with their religious institutions, such as churches, mosques or synagogues. These relationships should be attended to from the birth of the child, especially if the parents have committed to religious vows in their religious institution, such as the vows taken when a child is baptised.

Previous research has revealed that many people believe that parents' involvement in the creation of a disciplined school environment is needed in schools. A study conducted by Masingi (2017) revealed the following: "[B]oth learners and teachers mentioned parental involvement as the most effective strategy to curb indiscipline. Without parents' support, very little change will happen in terms of discipline. Parents must take responsibility and they must be at the forefront" (p. 86). This finding suggests that parents' perspectives can contribute positively to the creation of a disciplined school environment. A study conducted in Michigan about parents' perspectives on school discipline revealed that some parents regarded school discipline as negative when applied excessively (Bell, 2018). Parents' perceptions on whether discipline is progressive are also important. Parents should be given a chance to give feedback and participate in the discourse about how discipline can be effectively introduced and applied in schools. Salleh and Rosli (2019) discovered in their research that if parents were aware of their role and created an environment conducive to studying at home, they contributed to the remedying of problematic behaviour among learners. To a slightly lesser extent, this also applies to parents who communicate well with the school. The importance of effective parent-school communication was also stressed in a study pertaining to the relationship between parental involvement and learner discipline. Together with other forms of involvement (such as attending school meetings on discipline), parent-school communication plays a significant role in learner discipline control (Habyarimana & Andala, 2021). A lack of time on the part of the parents seems to be a significant obstacle in this regard (Sallah & Rosli, 2019).

One of the papers that dealt with the role of parents regarding learner discipline, an article by Wolhuter and Van der Walt (2020), contains a conceptual-theoretical reflection on the parental dimension. In their opinion, this dimension embraces four constituent factors: parenting style; the moral example parents set for their children; the family structure and dynamics; and parent-school relations, including parental involvement in school matters. Their investigation revealed that the moral example set by parents plays a key role in forming children's attitudes with respect to acceptable behaviour. With reference to the family structure and dynamics, their investigation showed that material and emotional stress in the family tends to lead to an increase in learner indiscipline at school. Their investigation also revealed that parental involvement and sound parent-school relations should be seen as essential ingredients in shaping learners' behaviour at school. Lastly, regarding the

conventional distinction between the three basic parenting styles (authoritarian, permissive and authoritative), they found that the authoritarian and permissive parenting styles tended to lead to ill discipline among learners at school, whereas the authoritative parenting style seemed to be best for promoting sound learner discipline in school.

The authoritative parenting style is characterised by a combination of high control and high responsiveness. The control of authoritative parents is cooperative and assertive (Febiyanti & Rachmawati, 2020). The answer to whether authoritative parenting characteristics are better than those of other styles depends on the cultural context in which parenting occurs (Febiyanti & Rachmawati, 2020). There is empirical evidence that, apart from the cultural context, parents' parenting style is closely connected to their children's level of development. Rizka and Bacotang (2018) discovered a positive correlation between the authoritative parenting style and the social skills of young children, such as self-control and a positive attitude towards others. The authoritative and indulgent parenting styles, characterised by warmth, lead to better psychosocial adjustment, such as a positive self-concept and level of well-being, than non-warm parenting styles (Garcia et al., 2020). This provides a sufficient rationale for including the authoritative parenting style in research on parents' views on discipline.

It is clear from this conceptual-theoretical framework that parents (or other educators, such as caregivers) are confronted with a momentous duty to guide their children through all the pitfalls and challenges of their young lives. There is evidence, however, that parents seem to fail in this duty, mainly where the moral foundation of social life has collapsed, as has been the case in South Africa during the past two decades (see Moral Regeneration Movement, 2018; Saunderson-Meyer, 2016). While these moral shortcomings could not, in totality, be laid at the door of parents, it can be argued that they must share some of the blame.

The next section of this article reports on research in which parents themselves had their say on many of these issues. Their responses are used to answer four research questions: 1) What views do parents have on the state of discipline of their children at home? 2) What views do parents have on managing learner discipline in school? 3) What relationship exists between these views? 4) What role does the authoritative parenting style play in parents' views on discipline issues?

Method of investigation

Instrument

A self-constructed questionnaire was developed to investigate South African parents' perspectives on the discipline of their children, both at home and in school. In formulating items for the questionnaire, we drew on two sets of sources. The first was a questionnaire on learner discipline in schools that had been developed, tested and refined by the research group at the North-West University in South Africa. This questionnaire was used to discover teachers' perspectives on learner discipline in schools (Wolhuter & Van Staden, 2007). This source provided the first part of the questionnaire, containing four sub-sections: 1) respondents' views on the state, causes and effects of learner discipline problems at their children's schools; 2) respondents' views on the state of discipline of their children at home; 3) respondents' views on the management of learner discipline in schools; and 4) respondents' views on the role of parents in curbing the discipline problems of their children at school.

The second source of material for the items in the questionnaire was the Parenting Styles and Dimensions Questionnaire (PSQD) of Robinson et al. (2001). A slightly adapted

version of the PSQD formed the second part of the questionnaire. This part was meant to determine the parenting style of the respondents. The respondents were also asked to provide some relevant biographical details.

The instrument consisted of Likert-type scale items and open-ended qualitative questions. The Likert scale employed was “never”, “once in a while”, “about half of the time” and “always”. A mixed-method approach was followed in that open-ended questions were added to the quantitative items (Creamer, 2018; Creswell & Plano Clark, 2018). The items of the questionnaire were derived from a previously developed theoretical framework that focused on learner discipline at home and in the school context.

Data collection

Two provinces of South Africa were selected for this project: North-West and Mpumalanga. The findings of this study can, therefore, not be summarily generalised to the entire country. A purposive sampling (non-probability) strategy was used to select different research sites and participants, as it was not feasible to use (stratified) random sampling owing to the Covid-19 pandemic at the time. Specific schools were targeted based on their availability. The research sites included ex-Model C schools, township schools and rural schools. Questionnaires were distributed to the schools for dissemination to parents. They were distributed in ways that minimised direct human contact during the pandemic. The completed questionnaires were collected from the schools on appointed dates. At each school, a sample was drawn from its parent corps. Sixteen schools and 448 parents in total responded favourably.

Data processing

Survey data analysis software was used to analyse the data. The Statistical Package for the Social Sciences was used to analyse the quantitative data, and validity analysis and reliability analysis were employed. In the processing of the data, the following had to be considered: Many cells in the database were empty (representing missing data) as the respondents had not reacted to statements. It was decided beforehand that questionnaires lacking responses to more than 10% of the 90 statements (apart from the biographical information) would be removed from the database. This left a total of 402 of the original 448 questionnaires in the database.

In N=70 cases, respondents did not closely follow the guidelines given for completing specific items of the questionnaire. The resulting incorrect responses were eliminated from the database.

Validity and reliability

Exploratory factor analysis was applied to both parts and four sections of the questionnaire to establish the validity thereof. Cronbach’s alphas were computed to establish the reliability (stability) of the extracted factors.

In the context of this article, it is essential to report the validity and reliability of two questionnaire elements. This concerns the subscale ‘authoritative parenting style’ and the section ‘the state of discipline of their children at home’.

Because minor changes were made to the wording of some of the statements belonging to the PSQD scale ‘authoritative style’, the alpha score of this scale of 27 items (see Appendix 1) was recalculated. The result of that calculation was a satisfactory 0.877.

To measure the scale ‘discipline at home’, a forced one-factor solution had to be run for the relevant section of the questionnaire, and items with a communality score lower than

0.25 were deleted. This yielded a single factor consisting of an eight-item scale (see Table 1) that reflected the state of discipline of children at home. The alpha score for that factor was satisfactory (0.761).

The third relevant scale, ‘discipline in school’, also required a one-factor solution to result in a valid measure. The alpha score of the four items that reflect ‘management of learner discipline in school’ (see Table 2) was 0.650.

Results

The relevant parts of the dataset that resulted in the administration of the questionnaire are used to answer the research questions. As described above, doing so concerns three distinct scales: ‘authoritative parenting style’, ‘discipline at home’ and ‘discipline in school’. First, the results of the second and third scales are presented per item. Then, the results of the three scales are related to each other.

Table 1 shows the results of the individual items of the scale ‘discipline at home’. The numbers and percentages for each position on the Likert scale are given per item. For each item, the percentages for the categories ‘I partially agree’ and ‘I agree’ together are at least 89. This result also applies to the total mean.

Table 1
Results of the items of the scale ‘discipline at home’

Items	I disagree		I partially disagree		I partially agree		I agree	
	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%
4.1 The atmosphere in my home is casual and not stressful.	24	6	17	4	79	20	277	69
4.2 I know what the basic rights of my child are according to the Constitution of our country.	14	3	18	4	42	10	323	80
4.3 I see our home as a place where we depend on one another.	18	4	19	5	63	16	299	74
4.4 I see our home as a place where everyone can live and exist meaningfully.	29	7	15	4	49	12	304	76
4.5 I insist on good discipline at home.	13	3	8	2	51	13	329	82
4.6 My approach to acceptable moral behaviour is to encourage my child to follow examples of good morals in his/her surroundings.	5	1	10	2	48	12	334	83

4.7 My approach to teaching acceptable morals is that parents have to teach their children good behaviour.	5	1	8	2	47	12	341	85
4.8 My approach to inculcating acceptable morals in my child is that teachers should help learners adopt acceptable moral behaviour.	16	4	12	3	76	19	294	73
Total mean	16	4	13	3	57	14	313	78

Table 2 shows the results of the individual items of the scale ‘discipline in school’. The numbers and percentages for each position on the Likert scale are given per item. For each item and for the total mean, the percentages for the categories ‘I partially agree’ and ‘I agree’ together are mostly above 80, except one (“I get information about discipline issues at my child’s school from teachers and the management of the school”) with 72%.

Table 2
Results of the items of the scale ‘discipline in school’

Items	I disagree		I partially disagree		I partially agree		I agree	
	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%
5.1 I keep myself informed about discipline issues in schools.	39	10	26	7	98	25	236	59
5.2 I get information about discipline issues at my child’s school from teachers and the management of the school.	75	19	36	9	68	17	221	55
5.3 My child’s school sufficiently involves parents in learner discipline matters.	31	8	42	11	78	20	244	62
5.4 The parent component of the governing body of my child’s school is absolutely strict with children.	26	7	39	10	93	24	233	60
Total mean	43	11	36	9	84	22	234	59

While the previous two tables show the results of the individual items of both scales at the ordinal level, Table 3 shows the results of both scales at the interval level. The average score of Scale 1 is greater than that of Scale 2, but the response spread is clearly smaller. Table 3 also shows the results of the Pearson correlation calculation. The correlation is not particularly high, but it is significant.

Table 3
Descriptive statistics and correlation of two scales

Scale	<i>n</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>	1	2
1. The state of discipline of your children at home	402	3.67	0.46	—	
2. The management of learner discipline in school	402	3.27	0.72	.32*	—

* $p < .01$.

The ‘authoritative parenting style’ scale has been dichotomised to use it as an independent variable. The average score is 3.53. The lower scores are called ‘low authoritative’, and above the average, ‘high authoritative’ (see Table 4).

ANOVA applied to the respondents’ scores on the authoritative parenting scale with the dichotomised authoritative scale as an independent variable shows that the means of the high authoritative group (3.74) are significantly higher than the means of the low authoritative group (3.16): $F(1,400) = 366.54$, $p < .001$. The effect size is very large (-1.983). The conclusion is that the groups in the independent variable differ significantly.

ANOVA applied to the respondents’ scores on the scale ‘The state of discipline of your children at home’ with the dichotomised authoritative scale as an independent variable shows that the means of the high authoritative group (3.81) are significantly higher than the means of the low authoritative group (3.43): $F(1,400) = 77.31$, $p < .001$. The effect size is large (-0.909).

ANOVA applied to the respondents’ scores on the scale ‘The management of learner discipline in school’ with the dichotomised authoritative scale as an independent variable shows that the means of the high authoritative group (3.46) are significantly higher than the means of the low authoritative group (2.97): $F(1,400) = 47.69$, $p < .001$. The effect size is medium (-0.713).

Table 4
Results of the three scales combined

Relevant scales	Low authoritative (N=149)		High authoritative (N=253)		Total (N=402)	
	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>
Authoritative parenting scale	3.16	.45	3.74	0.13	3.53	0.41
The state of discipline of your children at home	3.43	.59	3.81	0.27	3.67	0.46
The management of learner discipline in school	2.97	.76	3.46	0.64	3.27	0.72

Answers to the research questions

To answer the first research question (What views do parents have on the state of discipline of their children at home?), the results of the scale ‘discipline at home’ are helpful. The mean score on this scale was very high (3.67 out of a maximum of 4.00). Apparently, the respondents deem the state of discipline of their children at home to be very positive. The responses to the individual items of this scale also indicate this. The respondents’ characterisation of their family provides a reasonable basis for instilling discipline in their children. The atmosphere in their home is casual, they are aware of the rights of their children, they see their home as a place where family members depend on one another, and they see their home as a place where everyone can live and exist meaningfully. In addition, they insist on good discipline at home, and they encourage their children to follow examples of good morals in their surroundings. In addition to the task they see for themselves in teaching good behaviour, they believe teachers should help. This image corresponds to what was stated in the background sketch: parents should be involved to curb indiscipline (Masingi, 2017). In this study, involvement is evident in creating a home situation in which warmth, discipline and a good example from the parents play a major role. It can be concluded from the data that parents are aware of their task towards their children. This awareness is vital for preventing and dealing with discipline problems at school (Sallah & Rosli, 2019). The parents’ responses indicate a sound basis for instilling learner discipline in the school situation.

The second research question is: What views do parents have on managing learner discipline in school? A look at the results of the scale ‘discipline in school’ shows a high mean score (3.27 out of a maximum of 4.00). The reactions on the individual items of this scale reveal the meaning of this fact. The respondents in this study believe that the parent component of the governing body is strict with children. The respondents are very positive about managing learner discipline issues in their children’s schools. Parents keep themselves informed about discipline issues in their children’s schools. Staff members of their children’s schools inform them about discipline issues. The respondents feel themselves involved in discipline matters in their children’s schools. These results agree with what is stated in the background sketch, namely that parental involvement in discipline issues in school is necessary. The fact that good parent–school communication is essential for a school climate in which discipline prevails also emerges from these research results.

The third research question flows logically from the first two questions: What relationship exists between these views? To answer this question, a correlation coefficient was computed, which shows a significant positive correlation between the two views expressed in the results of the two scales. This correlation indicates that respondents with a less favourable view of their home situation also have a less optimistic view of managing learner discipline issues in their children’s schools. However, the reverse also applies; parents who view their interaction with their children positively also view the way the school deals with discipline issues more positively. There appears to be a positive correlation between parents’ views on the educational climate in their family and the state and management of discipline in their children’s schools. In the background sketch, such a relation was supposed, and this study supports this assumption.

The last research question to answer is: What role does the authoritative parenting style play in parents’ views on discipline issues? This study reveals the effect of the authoritative parenting style on the views of parents on discipline issues at home and in school. Parents with a highly authoritative parenting style show a much more positive view of the discipline of their children at home than parents with a lower authoritative style. The same is the case concerning the second scale. Parents with a highly authoritative parenting

style express a much more positive perspective on managing learner discipline in their child's school than parents with a less authoritative style. As stated in the background sketch, there is evidence of the essential role of an authoritative parenting style in promoting sound learner discipline in school. The outcome of this study seems to support the importance of the authoritative parenting style. The extent to which they use the authoritative parenting style matters for both parents' views on their educational situation in the family and their views on the state and management of learner discipline in school.

Retrospection and a possible way forward

The home situation described by the respondents in this study should provide a sound starting point for preventing and dealing with discipline problems at school. Whether the home situation really forms such a starting point is not clear from the data. It was beyond the scope of this study to look for a relationship between the home situation of children and the occurrence of discipline problems at school. Further research could provide clues that may encourage parents to raise their children in a particular way.

Further research on learner discipline should be done since good parent-school communication is vital for a good school climate with reference to learner discipline. According to their views, this study showed that parents were well-informed about the situation at school. However, research also needs to be done into the views of teachers. After all, communication is two-sided. Therefore, communication regarding discipline issues should be a research subject.

If the authoritative parenting style contributes to a healthy and orderly parenting climate in the home and at school, parents should learn to use such a parenting style. The question is how that can happen and what role the school can play in this. Practice-orientated research can help find answers to this question.

Disclosure statement

The authors hereby declare that they have no financial or personal relationships with any party that could influence them detrimentally or beneficially in writing this article.

Data availability statement

The participants of this study did not give written consent for their data to be shared publicly; therefore, owing to the sensitive nature of the research, supporting data are not available.

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Appendix 1

Statements of the authoritative parenting style

- I encourage my child to talk about his/her troubles.
- I know the names of my child's friends.
- I give praise when my child displays good behaviour.
- I joke and play with my child.
- I show sympathy when my child is hurt or frustrated.
- I give comfort and understanding when my child is upset.
- I am easy-going and relaxed with my child.
- I tell my child what I expect from him/her even before he/she does something.
- I show patience with my child.
- I am aware of my child's needs and try to provide in them.
- I allow my child to help us make rules for the family.
- I give my child the reasons why rules should be obeyed.
- I tell my child when I am happy about something that he/she has done.
- I help my child to understand that he/she will reap what he/she has sown.
- I listen to what my child wants before I ask him/her to do something.
- I am aware of problems or concerns about my child in school.
- I show that I love my child by hugging, kissing and holding him/her.
- I tell my child that I am sorry when I have made a mistake as a parent.
- I have a discussion with my child when he/she has misbehaved.
- I have loving times with my child.
- I allow my child to talk to me as a parent when we disagree about something.
- I show respect to my child by telling him/her to say what he/she is thinking.
- I explain to my child how I feel about his/her good and bad behaviour.
- I listen to what my child likes before making plans for the family.
- I tell my child what he/she can expect if he/she is doing something in a particular way.
- I help my child to do more acceptable and better things.
- I make the importance of rules very clear to my child.